

solid mass separated after 24 hrs. The solid was filtered and recrystallised from alcohol; yield-about 60-70%. The relevant data are given in Table 1.

5-Nitro-4(2)-[4-oxo-6,8-disubstituted-3H-quinazolin-3-yl]-benzylidene malonylureas(V) :

A mixture of (IV) (0.01 mole) urea (0.01 mole) and ethanolic NaOEt (0.01 mole) was refluxed for 6-7 hrs on a steam bath and subsequently refluxed on oil bath for 16 hrs at 110-115°. The mixture then treated with 20 ml in hot dil. HCl and was kept in an ice-chest overnight. The solid was filtered and recrystallised from ethyl alcohol. The yield was about 60-70%. The relevant data are given in Table 1.

Antibacterial screening : All the compounds (V) were screened out for their antibacterial activity against *S. aureus*, using the method of Verma and Nobels^{1,2}. Zone of inhibition to these bacteria ranged between 5-15 mm for compounds Va, Vd, Ve, Vg and Vh. Compounds Vb, Vc and Vf were inactive. Compound Ve was found to be the best active (15 mm sterilization zone).

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Synthesis and CNS Activity of 1-(5'-Alkyl, 1', 3', 4'-thiadiazol-2'-yl), 2-methyl, 4-arylidene-imidazol-5-ones.

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FIFTEEN new thiadiazolyl imidazolone derivatives (III) have been synthesised by the condensation of some 2-methyl, 4-arylidene azalactones (I) with 2-amino, 5-alkyl-thiadiazoles (II) in pyridine. The 2-amino - thiadiazole¹⁻⁵ and imidazolone⁶⁻⁸ derivatives have been reported to possess various CNS activities. It was thought worthwhile to investigate whether the compounds having both imidazolone and thiadiazole moieties can have better pharmacological results. The reported MAO-inhibitory activity in imidazolone nucleus^{9,10}, guided the idea that the mechanism of action of the aforesaid compounds on parkinsonian features could be dopaminergic, therefore their MAO-inhibitory activity was also tested.

2-Amino, 5-alkyl-1, 3, 4-thiadiazoles : These were synthesised by the method of Funatsukuri *et al*¹¹.

2-Methyl, 4-arylidene-azlact-5-ones : These were synthesised using the procedure of Vogel¹², Herbert and Shemin¹³, Dakin¹⁴ and Niender and Ziering¹⁵.

1-(5'-Methyl, 1', 3', 4'-thiadiazol-2'-yl)-2'-methyl-4-(p-methoxy benzylidene)-imidazol-5-one :

2-Amino, 5-methyl 1, 3, 4-thiadiazole (0.01 mole) and 2-methyl, 4-(p-methoxy benzylidene)-azlact-5-one (0.01 mole) were taken in pyridine (15 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for about 6 hr on a sand bath. The excess of pyridine was distilled off at reduced pressure and the residue was cooled at room temperature. It was then poured in a mixture of 50 ml conc. HCl and 50 g ice and left overnight. The solid separated was filtered and recrystallised twice with ethanol and dried. Yield 70% ; m.p. 218-19°. IR(KBr) 1660 cm⁻¹ (for C=C stretch trisubstituted); 1680cm⁻¹ (for ring N-C- group of imidazolone moiety);

1640 cm⁻¹ (for ring C=N bonding). Similarly other 1-(5'-alkyl-1', 3', 4'-thiadiazol-2'-yl)-2-methyl-4-arylidene imidazol-5-ones were prepared and are described in Table 1.

Pharmacology : All the compounds were screened for CNS activity on albino mice of either sex. Acute toxicity test was also done and the ALD₅₀ of these compounds was also determined following the method of Weil¹⁶. ALD₅₀ are given in Table 1.

The compounds are relatively nontoxic. Compound Nos. 5,12,13 produced piloerection and stimulations

TABLE I--(5'-ALKYL, 1',3',4'-THIADIAZOL-2'-YL), 2-METHYL, 4-ARYLIDENE IMIDAZOL-5-ONES(III)

Compd. No.	Molecular formula	R ₁	R ₂	Melting* points (°C)	S%		N%		ALD ₅₀ (mg/kg wt of mice)
					Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	
R ₃ = CH ₃									
1.	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ ON ₄ S	H	H	164	11.27	11.02	19.71	19.52	> 1000
2.	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ ON ₄ SCl	H	<i>p</i> -Cl	219-20	10.04	10.23	17.58	17.29	> 1000
3.	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₄ S	H	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	218-19	10.17	10.22	17.80	17.72	1000
4.	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₄ S	H	<i>o</i> -OH	211-12	10.66	10.39	18.66	18.32	825
5.	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₄ S	<i>p</i> -OH	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	158-59	9.69	9.92	16.96	17.23	1000
R ₃ = C ₂ H ₅									
6.	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ ON ₄ S	H	H	187	10.73	10.92	18.79	18.29	825
7.	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ ON ₄ SCl	H	<i>p</i> -Cl	243-44	9.62	9.39	16.84	17.12	> 1000
8.	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄ S	H	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	165-66	9.75	9.65	17.07	17.43	681
9.	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₄ S	H	<i>o</i> -OH	235-36	10.19	10.32	17.83	17.53	825
10.	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄ S	<i>p</i> -OH	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	215	9.30	9.62	16.28	16.58	681
R ₃ = C ₃ H ₇									
11.	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ ON ₄ S	H	H	174-75	10.25	10.45	17.94	17.64	> 1000
12.	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ ON ₄ SCl	H	<i>p</i> -Cl	188	9.23	9.46	16.16	16.34	681
13.	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₄ S	H	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	196-97	9.36	9.12	16.37	16.49	681
14.	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄ S	H	<i>o</i> -OH	184-85	9.75	9.49	17.07	17.34	825
15.	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₄ S	<i>p</i> -OH	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	169-70	8.93	9.02	15.64	16.21	> 1000

* The melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Yield ranged between 60-70%.

on the CNS. Compound nos. 1, 2, 6 and 10 increased the rate of breathing at all doses. SMA and reactivity was increased by all the compounds at all doses.

These compounds were also tested for anti-tremorine activity but no significant results were obtained. They were also screened for their *in-vivo* mono-amine oxidase inhibitory activity against 'Reserpine' induced activity. All the compounds reversed the stimulating effects of reserpine at 3 hr after the dose given. However, the activity was negative at 18 hr observations after the drug administration.

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Chemical Constituents of the Stem bark of *Elaeodendron glaucum* Pers

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ELAEO DENDRON *glaucum* Pers (Celastraceae) is generally grown for its medicinal importance¹. The leaves are found to have a sternutatory and fumigatory action. They are also used as a snuff to relieve headache. The gum obtained from the plant dissolves in water to give an adhesive. A survey of literature revealed no work on this plant and hence an investigation of its stem bark was undertaken. We have obtained n-octacosanol, friedelin, β -sitosterol, betulonic acid, 23-hydroxy betulin, β -sitosterol- β -D-glucoside from the benzene extract and dulcitol from the alcohol extract of the stem bark.

The finely ground stem bark was extracted thoroughly with benzene followed by extraction with alcohol.

Benzene Extract :

This was concentrated under vacuum when a brown mass was obtained which was chromatographed over silica gel.

n-Octacosanol : Elution of the column with pet. ether-benzene (3:1) afforded n-octacosanol, white granules m.p. 83-4° (EtOAc), $C_{28}H_{58}O$, I.R., ν_{max}^{OH} : 3230, 730 and 720 cm^{-1} ; acetate ($Ac_2O/pyr.$), m.p. 64-5°.

Friedelin : Elution of the column with pet. ether-benzene (1:1) furnished friedelin, white microneedles, m.p. 258-60° (pet. ether), $C_{30}H_{50}O$, M^+ 426, I.R., ν_{max}^{KBr} : 1720 cm^{-1} ; oxime, m.p. 2 0-2°. It was identical (mmp, TLC and IR) with an authentic sample.

β -Sitosterol : Elution of the column with benzene yielded β -sitosterol, m.p. 136-7° (EtOH); acetate ($Ac_2O/pyr.$) 125-6°, identical (mmp and TLC) with an authentic sample.

Betulonic Acid : Elution of the column with benzene-ethyl acetate (1:1) furnished white crystals of betulonic acid m.p. 251-3° (C_6H_6 : EtOAc), found : C, 79.05; H, 10.25% $C_{30}H_{48}O_8$ requires C, 79.25; H, 10.20%. I.R., ν_{max}^{KBr} : 3100 (broad), 1710, 1690 cm^{-1} ; methyl ester (CH_2N_2), m.p. 162-3°, identical (mmp, TLC and IR) with an authentic sample.

23-Hydroxy betulin : Further elution of the column with benzene-ethyl acetate (1:1) yielded white microneedles of 23-hydroxybetulin, m.p. 256-8° (C_6H_6 : EtOAc), found : C, 78.80; H, 10.70% $C_{30}H_{50}O_8$ requires C, 78.55; H, 10.99%. I.R., ν_{max}^{KBr} : 3380 cm^{-1} ; acetate ($Ac_2O/pyr.$), amorphous, uncrystallizable, acetate group determination showed the presence of three hydroxy groups in the compound. Identical (mmp, TLC and IR) with an authentic sample.

β -Sitosterol- β -D-glucoside : Elution of the column with ethylacetate-methanol (1:1) furnished white microneedles of β -sitosterol- β -D-glucoside, m.p. 290-2° (MeOH), found : C, 72.79; H, 10.23% $C_{35}H_{60}O_6$ requires C, 72.91; H, 10.41%. I.R., ν_{max}^{KBr} : 3400 cm^{-1} ; acetate, m.p. 166°. On acidic hydrolysis, β -sitosterol, m.p. 135-7°, identical (mmp and TLC) with an authentic sample and glucose (Co-paper chromatography) were obtained.

Alcohol Extract :

Dulcitol : The concentrated extract when kept in a refrigerator for 48 hours deposited a white solid. On recrystallisation, it yielded dulcitol, white shining crystals, m.p. 185-6° (50% EtOH); hexaacetate ($Ac_2O/pyr.$), m.p. 166-8°. It was identical (mmp and paper chromatography) with an authentic sample.

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